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**THE EXPOSURE OF REGULAR READING TO ENHANCE SELF LEARNING
TECHNIQUES IN REAL TIME SITUATIONS FOR SECOND LANGUAGE LEARNERS**

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ABSTRACT

Language is a means of communication to share our ideas, thoughts to access the related information in the fields of science and technology, business, trade, commerce etc., Many scientific inventions, discoveries and enormous wealth of knowledge stored in libraries and internet facilitate the learners to enhance the knowledge all over the world. English plays a major role as a link language to meet the requirements of different topics to suit the taste of the people to read in the printed form or internet generated online web pages. To relish the taste of the language certain basic structures related in the boundaries of grammar, syntax, lexical patterns with a trace of vocabulary awareness have to be cultivated through regular reading habits. Reading is an excellent process of active participation of interaction between the reader and the writer to comprehend the printed version of the texts in a logical way. Reading involves the ability to use strategies such as visual insight of key words, phrases, fast eye-movements to grasp the central idea of the given topic. The more the student reads, with longer duration of print exposure , develops the concentration levels and confidence to acquire fast reading to get rough idea of the topic through skimming, scanning the accurate information to form ideas of visual information of semantic mapping in the mind.

The study mainly focuses on the students reading habits to implant self learning techniques and strategies to read independently, to improve automatic retention of vocabulary, grammar and comprehension abilities. Research studies showed that the students who nourish in print rich atmosphere have greater competence in varied aspects of language learning including vocabulary, syntax, spellings knowledge of literature, culture, history etc., through practical methods. An Extensive reading has a wide aspect of learning especially outside the classroom hours to motivate and encourage learners to read enormous literature on various topics of interest.

A sample study was conducted in three different Engineering colleges at B.Tech level in various aspects of learning. The workshop was conducted for a week to test their proficiency levels such as grammar, vocabulary and usage of words in different contexts. They were asked to read books on different topics graded at their cognitive levels with the mention of glossary at the end of each lesson. The research findings revealed that the students enjoyed reading books with simple vocabulary with lots of pictures, graphs and lively dialogues through practical teaching methods. The students tried to grasp the textual information through innovative thinking of individual ideas and thoughts through discussion, goals of reading, underlining the points in a strategical way of comprehending the texts. This clearly states that the students reading their selected materials in a relaxed tension free environment develop cognitive and Meta-cognitive strategies such as semantic mapping, visual perception of words, Skimming, Scanning the relevant information through incidental unconscious retention of language proficiency..

KEYWORDS: CALL, Cognitive, Meta-Cognitive, Skimming, Scanning.

INTRODUCTION

English plays a major role of widely accepted spoken and written language to exchange and share our ideas placed on top international reputation in various fields such as science and Technology, Business, Medicine etc., with the arrival of (CALL)(computer assisted Language learning), the English language teaching has wide applicability to build effective relations to utilise the innovative teaching methods. The wide usage of Computers with the internet facility monitors the students language proficiency with proper guidance from teachers to implement their inherent skills and strategies. This paper mainly sheds light on the students reading habits, sets goal of reading and develop their inner talents such as cognitive and Meta-Cognitive skills. Reading is an interactive process of understanding the comprehension passages, short stories, Biographies etc., to unravel the aesthetic beauty of thrilling plots, scenes, interesting characters with marvelous expression of lively dialogues, emotions, culture of the written language. The main focus is to implement a positive attitude of reading culture of print rich environment to excel their language potency in the areas of spellings, syntactical structures, easy vocabulary of graded materials with lots of pictures, graphics through general understanding rather than memorization or evaluation of texts in detail.

Extensive reading “is generally associated with reading large amounts with the aim of getting an overall understanding of the material” (Bamford and Day 1997). [01]. This clearly states that Extensive reading provides the learners with enormous variety of books graded to their level of understanding with minimum support of Dictionary. The research study proved that silent uninterrupted reading of varied kinds of genre develops automaticity such as fast reading, recognition of keywords, phrases with excellent command over the language which facilitates the reader to get familiar with words repeated in different contexts to heighten the readers awareness of vocabulary to produce meaningful paragraphs, essays, short stories and better communication abilities.

INTENSIVE VS EXTENSIVE READING

Intensive reading is defined as reading a text under the close supervision of the teacher, read the passages, refer the dictionary for the meanings, grammar, vocabulary in detail to build language proficiency. The students are provided the same text throughout the year to attend the syntactical, lexical and grammatical construction of sentences in detail. It is teacher centred and wait for the teacher’s instructions to apply the skills and strategies to carry out the tasks. The students read the same teacher selected materials whether they like it or not and the proficiency of learning has no scope to judge a fluent or an average reader. The main concept is to judge their fluency of reading and to motivate their inner talents to judge their independent learning to register the key concepts of automatic retention of vocabulary through regular reading habits.

Extensive reading provides the learners to practical approach of pleasure reading in a tension free environment to choose books from a variety of topics such as Books, Journals, Magazines, Biographies, comics etc., to enhance fast reading, recognize the key sentences, words, phrases for general understanding rather than the literary excellence. The findings on Extensive reading has proved that more the student reads the more retention of vocabulary takes place and develops certain strategies such as to predict the content of the story, title, chapter etc., through semantic mapping, fast eye-movements to grasp the central idea of selected topic.

Significance of the study :

The research study tries to exemplify the significance of Extensive reading related to various aspects of practical methods of teaching the students to bring out their latent skills and strategies to tackle the texts at their level of understanding. The materials are to be graded on a variety of topics to facilitate the students to read independently in class or outside the classroom hours to build automatic retention of vocabulary, comprehension etc., to escalate their strategical methods of retrieving the information from the texts to establish logical aspects of intellectual calibre.

Research Findings :

The Findings of the study was conducted on 250 students of three different Engineering colleges at B.Tech level at PRRM Engineering College, Geethanjali College of Engineering & Technology and Hi-Point College of Engineering & Technology in Moinabad. The students were given different tasks on reading. Grammar, vocabulary etc., to make them realize the significance of Extensive Reading to employ their individual talents to tackle the texts in varied aspects of learning. The Sample consists of the students mostly from the rural areas who select English as the second or Third Language and require proper reading skills or strategies to establish regular reading habits.

Besides, the second sample consists of the students who opt English as the First Language with a reasonable background of Language input to comprehend the printed materials at their level of understanding. The workshop was conducted for a week to make them realize the positive attitudes of print rich environment to motivate their inner talents in varied fields such as Grammar, vocabulary, spellings etc., As a Pre-reading activity, the students were taught to choose books from the various genres ranging from Short stories, Novels, Biographies etc., to encourage their confidence levels of free voluntary reading. The students were trained to assess the length, language and vocabulary to read as many books as possible. The materials were simplified versions of the original texts graded carefully with the mention of glossary at the end of each lesson. The students were given some tips to learn Pre-fixes and Suffixes to establish formal reading activities to carefully choose through a variety of Books, Magazines etc., whether the vocabulary and language is matched to their level of understanding. Students were instructed to maintain a reading log to note down the comments, remarks through discussions, asking questions and their individual opinions to activate their background knowledge especially in the areas of characters, plots, lively dialogues etc., and to reject the texts which lacks interest and enjoyment to fulfill the learner requirements.

S.NO	TEXT/TITLE OF THE TEXT	AVERAGE	GOOD	REMARKS
01	MAGAZINES			
02	COMICS			
03	JOURNALS			
04	INTERNET WEB PAGES			
05	FICTION/ NON-FICTION			

Activity [No. 01]. The students were given a task to inculcate free voluntary reading to activate their background knowledge to predict the index, headings, title of the chapter at glance for active participation of reading culture. The task was given from the lesson “ The secret of work” a Biography of Swami Vivekananda an Indian Hindu Monk from the 1st year B.Tech “Epitome of Wisdom” [P.NO.118-120] about 350 words. As a Pre-reading activity the students were asked to guess the topic, express their ideas by looking at the cover page, title, index, headings and sub-headings to activate their schematic knowledge. After reading the lesson the students were given a task to identify the grammatical structures, words and phrases and to frame sentences using the unknown words and phrases meaningfully. The glossary of unknown words were mentioned at the end of each chapter. The students were taught to utilize the simple tips such as formation of words from noun to Adjective such as “Circle as a noun and Circular as an Adjective will automatically develop their positive attitude towards the print exposure, repeated words in different contexts to accentuate their language proficiency

Activity [No.02]

Students were given a task to recognize the grammatical patterns, meanings of the following sentences to test their proficiency of learning using clues to activate their background knowledge to cope up with the printed texts.

Example:

1. Ongole is famous ----- [of,for] bulls (Suitable Preposition)
2. The Examination section is short of -----[Stationary, Stationery] (Suitable word)
3. His Wife came ----- [latter/ later] than him. (Suitable word)
4. The rose ----- [is smelling/smells] sweet. [Suitable verb/Tense].

The study has clearly mentioned that the students tried to guess the central idea of the story by looking at the title, chapter, headings, skip the unknown words to extract and evaluate the information at their level of understanding. The students with English as the second language were comparatively slow to select the reading materials, identify the key sentences, words, phrases and in the areas of spellings, grammar and pronunciation. On the other hand, the students with English as the First Language showed improvement to apply the relevant strategies and skills to focus their language potency such as fast reading, identify the usage of words in different contexts and to analyse the information from the written language. At the End of the programme the study revealed that there is consistency of errors in the spheres of grammar, spellings and pronunciation of words on both levels of instruction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gatbonton and Segalowitz (2005) conclude from his study that the readers could acquire implicit vocabulary gain from extensive reading both quantitatively and qualitatively as well as improve their attitudes toward reading. [02]. This clearly focus on the students reading habits to select and read independently to spot out the main points, words, phrases to gain command over the language through visual recognition to grasp the overall subject content rather than the language. The main aspect of Extensive reading is to expose the readers to print rich graded materials to be included in the curriculum or outside the classroom hours with simple vocabulary of two to three unknown words in a page to develop fast reading, recognize the sentences, phrases, idioms etc., to have control over the language to express their constructive thoughts and ideas. Researchers have claimed that the students who cultivate the habit of reading culture will automatically build certain skills and strategies such as evaluating, analyzing the length of the materials, mental processing through bottom up and top-down processes, skimming, Scanning etc., Bottom up process relates to guess the context, identify the sentence patterns, words phrases through visual mapping in the mind from the texts and top-down process involves to use their cognitive and meta-cognitive strategies to relate the textual information as the readers experience with the print exposure will transmit the information, knowledge emotion and culture of the written language.

Anderson and Pearson maintain that “a reader’s schemata, or knowledge already stored in memory, function in the process of interpreting new information and allowing it to enter and become a part of the knowledge store (p.255).” [03]. The texts facilitates the readers to give the directions to recall and construct the meanings to employ their schematic knowledge, feelings, emotions of the graphic presentation of the written language. The more the exposure of the printed materials will enhance their expertise of the subject knowledge in the relevant fields such as linguistic, structural construction of sentences, syntax, decode the printed words in the form of graphic signs, tables to guess the index, subheadings etc., through a wide range of materials to judge whether the language and vocabulary is suited to their level of understanding. Graded materials with lots of animated pictures, lively dialogues, short stories, comics etc., specially designed for the students of English as a second language will automatically activate their relevant schematic knowledge to become effective readers and writers.

Escribano (1999) states that through reading we have the opportunity of being exposed to well – organized and well – written pieces of writing which help us to improve our language abilities and to build writing schemata. [04]. Extensive reading facilitates the readers to have a general overview of the textual information to effectively integrate their cognitive and Meta-cognitive levels of thinking to frame meaningful paragraphs, essays, short stories etc., The teachers play a vital role to activate their background knowledge and inculcate the habit of regular reading to become self-reliant and better readers. The research findings have revealed that Extensive reading is the best way to acquire language proficiency and vocabulary development as the students become aware of the varied shades of meanings in different contexts as the meaning of words change according to the situation and context.

Carrell and Eisterhold (1983) state that accessing appropriate content schemata depends initially on “the graphic display” which “must be somehow reconstructed by the reader as meaningful language” (p. 562). [05]. A fluent reader improves certain strategies and skills on repeated exposure of the printed materials and try to focus on the related information to recognize the words, phrases and idiomatic expressions of previously stored background knowledge, link the textual information to gain complete command over the language. Therefore, the teachers have to design the curriculum based on the students reading habits, activate their background knowledge to read books graded to their level of understanding. The main objective of Extensive reading is to guide the students to select books which create pleasure, greater awareness of the reading materials with proper guidance from the teachers to develop their inherent skills and strategies to skip the unknown words or passages and establish an habit of general understanding rather than literary excellence. In other words, students learn to become self- reliant and a process of pragmatic methods of teaching can be enhanced through certain tasks such as Pre-reading, While reading and Post reading activities to motivate their schematic knowledge of independent learning of the target language. In Pre-reading activity the teacher tries to motivate the students curiosity of learning to link the passages or the topic of the text through discussions, identify the titles, sub headings and the chronology of events or characters which occur in the plot of the story, asking questions , create awareness of the text to motivate their interest in the form of pictures,

slides, movies etc., This will automatically help students to recognize the words, phrases, syntax and usage of words in different contexts as the reader realizes the importance of extensive reading is an ideal way to learn varied shades of meanings to flourish their language proficiency. The second stage i.e., the While reading activity the students try to employ the relevant strategies and skills to cope up with the textual information through discussions to express their ideas and thoughts in a clear manner. In the post- reading activity the students link their schematic knowledge with the textual knowledge through the use of cloze exercises, cut up sentences and to tackle the comprehension questions through practical method. This method of teaching through practical methods will naturally build their inborn talents to browse the texts with its cover page, title, sub headings etc., and to judge whether the vocabulary is suited to their level of understanding.

Lomicka (1998: 41) gave the definition more concretely “typically located in the side or bottom margins, glosses are most often supplied for ‘unfamiliar’ words, which may help to limit continual dictionary consultation that may hinder and interrupt the L2 reading comprehension process”. [06]. This clearly states that the students have to be provided with a variety of books on a wide range of topics with the mention of glossary at the end of each lesson. Graded materials are the simplified versions of original texts specially designed for the students of English as a second language to engage students in active participation of regular reading habits.

The main objective of Extensive reading is to make the students to judge their own reading material on a broad variety of graded materials with simple vocabulary with lots of pictures, animated short stories, biographies etc., The research findings have proved that the students develop certain skills and strategies such as predicting, set goals of reading, analyzing, decode the meanings, syntax etc., through the interaction of the written language.

Extensive reading which is mostly conducted outside the classroom hours where the students are encouraged to read books or internet web pages i.e., e-books (Electronic books) on a wide spectrum of printed materials such as Novels, Biographies, comics, short stories to read extensively in a tension free environment. Reading is an active skill to grasp the information from the text and the reader brings the information, culture, emotion of the writer’s opinion and thoughts through interaction of the written language. Extensive reading provides the learners with varied topics of texts to read quantitatively and qualitatively to gain vocabulary, identify the phrases, words, idioms etc., The students have a wider scope of practical methods of learning to develop their skills and strategies of the reading process through various Multimedia internet electronically generated web pages, download videos on short stories, biographies, speeches of fluent speakers, grammar exercises, quiz programmes etc., to check their pronunciation, spellings and command over the language. Teachers can support their interest of learning to participate in certain tasks such as picture description, writing the short stories, recording their voices, debates, role plays to produce meaningful essays, paragraphs, reports etc., Therefore, the materials have to be carefully selected and graded for the students of English as a second language with more practical methods of teaching with the mention of glossary of unknown words at the end of each lesson. A specially designed curriculum has to be implemented where students engage for longer periods of silent uninterrupted reading to build their Cognitive and Meta-Cognitive strategies. The continuous exposure of printed materials will naturally make them independent readers to select their own materials, identify the goals of reading, accurate visual perception of words, phrases, fast eye-movements with minimum support of the teachers makes students realize the individual talents to become better readers.

LIMITATIONS

The findings of the study conducted in the rural areas of Moinabad revealed that students lacked proper reading habits. The workshop conducted for a week on students reading habits and to implement the Extensive reading programme to activate their inner talents, design suitable curriculum to motivate their individual talents to cope up with the reading materials graded to their level of understanding. Teachers have to guide the students to choose books and support their active participation of reading to tackle the texts through analyzing, evaluating and scanning the materials to judge whether the language and vocabulary suited to their level of understanding. The findings of the study had clearly showed that the students lacked in certain spheres of learning such as to apply the relevant skills and strategies to select books, recognize the words, phrases, identify the title, sub-headings etc., with few mistakes in grammar and usage of vocabulary. The students were trained to choose books with simple vocabulary on varied topics with lots of pictures, animated graphics at the initial stages of learning. Gradually, the

continuous exposure of reading materials on different topics will naturally build their confidence to read books beyond their level of understanding.

Therefore, the readers have to employ their suitable skills and strategies to analyse and evaluate their own reading materials, browse through internet, watch News channels, listen to lectures on varied topics, animated short stories etc., which will enable them to realize their weakness to solve their problems for effective control and command over the language. This will automatically build their process of learning through enquiry, social interaction, discussion to gain awareness of the knowledge through commitment, strategic learning, devote time on reading to become confident and successful life-long readers.

SUGGESTIONS

The Research Findings have clearly illustrated that the students achieve their language proficiency who engage in longer duration of uninterrupted silent reading and utilize their suitable skills and strategies such as to identify the goals of reading, grasp the central idea of the subject content, analyse and extract the textual information through practical methods to activate their inner talents. The study focussed on the students reading habits and to flood learners with enormous variety of graded materials on topics with lots of pictures, animated short stories, biographies etc. to motivate their confidence for general awareness of the target language and judge their proficiency level of understanding. The research on Extensive reading has proved that the students exposure to print media would give them an ample scope to build automatic retention of word power as the reader comes across repeated words in different contexts in short stories, biographies, magazines etc., The main objective of Extensive reading which is mostly conducted outside the classroom activity to facilitate the students to read their selected books with easy vocabulary. Teachers have to take initiative to make students realize the importance of reading culture to include the suitable graded materials in the curriculum to identify their weakness, solve their problems through practical methods like Pre-reading, While-reading and Post-reading activities. This will automatically encourage students to develop positive attitude for free voluntary reading which enable them to capture their attention in the reading environment to comprehend the word usage, collocations, idiomatic phrases etc., to become self-reliant life-long readers.

CONCLUSION

The study conducted for a week on Extensive reading Programme has clearly emphasized that the students have to be provided with the texts on wide topics to read in a tension free environment to express their ideas and thoughts in a clear manner. The findings of study focused on the students reading habits and to select the materials on a wide range of topics available in texts or internet web pages with the guidance of teachers to check whether the vocabulary is suited to their level of understanding. The texts acts as a tool to provide the linguistic input as the reader brings the information, knowledge and culture such as to grasp the material through constructive thinking, decode the meaning etc., with the relevant schematic knowledge to comprehend the texts. Researchers have claimed that the students with more exposure to the printed materials will automatically build their own cognitive and Meta-cognitive strategies to judge the materials through analyzing, extracting the subject content through discussions with peers, fast eye-movements, scanning the title, sub-headings, tables, graphs etc., Therefore, Extensive Reading is an excellent way to engage and attract the students interest for longer periods of silent uninterrupted reading environment to improve confidence and motivation in all spheres of learning.

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